

CAPILLARY EFFECTS IN LIQUID COMPOSITE MOULDING WITH NON-CRIMP FABRICS

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ABSTRACT

When a part is being processed via RTM, many phenomena occur during its impregnation. Two types of flow are often noticed during impregnation, a macroflow, taking place between the tows that compose the fabric, and a micro flow, taking place inside the tows. The two different flows progress at different rates, as they are influenced by the capillary pressures acting within the tows. Capillary forces thus play a role in LCM process, even though they are often neglected. The present work aims at determining the capillary effects acting on Non-Crimp Fabrics (NCF) during infiltration by a matrix. For this purpose, the slug flow assumption is taken, hence the micro- and macro-flow are not distinguished. Three types of liquids are used to impregnate the dry fabric. The first one is polyethylene glycol (PEG) dissolved in water, providing a Newtonian model fluid. The second one is a commercial thermoset epoxy resin and the third one is thermoplastic PA12 system in monomer and activator form. In this article, results will be presented on the capillary pressure determination for the three-fluid/NCF systems.

KEYWORDS

Resin Transfer Moulding; Impregnation; Capillary Pressure; Permeability & Non-Crimp Fabrics.

INTRODUCTION

Responding to the recent introduction of low cost carbon fibres, automotive industry has now taken the initiative to co-operate on a European level in an attempt to enable the use of composite materials in fully load bearing, main automotive structures such as the Body-in-White (BIW). The effort focuses on low volume series of 50 units per day using high-speed low cost Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) processes. The European project TECABS (Technologies for Carbon fibre reinforced modular automotive structures) aims at reducing the weight of the BIW by 50%. Using complex shaped multifunctional parts and smart joining technologies, the number of parts can be reduced to 30% of the present 200+. The reinforcement is in the form of carbon fibre non-crimp fabrics (NCF) since they have the highest potential in mechanical strength and drapability to fulfil requirements linked to the manufacture of structural components of the BIW [1-5]. Two matrix materials are investigated in this project: an epoxy thermoset and a thermoplastic PA12 polymerised in situ.

Infiltration is the process that governs the manufacture of components made via RTM techniques. Amongst the phenomena involved during infiltration, capillary effects are often neglected for polymer matrices because they have a low surface tension, but they may however exert a non-negligible role.

The capillary effects have been extensively studied in soil science and hydrology. The capillary pressure drop corresponds to the work needed to replace a gas by a liquid within a porous medium [6]. Sometimes, spontaneous infiltration, also termed wicking, can take place.

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It corresponds to a negative capillary pressure drop ($\Delta P_\gamma < 0$). If this drops is positive ($\Delta P_\gamma > 0$), then a certain threshold pressure must be overcome for the infiltration to happen. The capillary pressure drop is defined thermodynamically by:

$$\Delta P_\gamma = -S_f \gamma_{ma} \cos(\theta) \quad (1)$$

Where γ_{ma} is the surface tension between the matrix and the atmosphere and S_f is the area of matrix-fibre interface per unit volume, and θ is the wetting angle. Equation (1) is defined statically. It represents the pressure difference at this infiltration front. In practice however, during an infiltration experiment, these forces act at different scales of matrix-fibre interface since the pore distribution is not a narrow function, and there is a range of pressures over which infiltration occurs. This gradual filling of the porous bed has been largely studied in soil mechanics, but several authors have also discussed this topic in composites [7].

Capillary pressures can be measured via two techniques. When a system has reached a thermodynamic equilibrium then equation (1) can be used, and the capillary pressure can be determined via the measurement of the contact angle. Surface tension can be easily determined using a Wilhelmy microbalance, but S_f is a value which is difficult to measure accurately. One must be aware that the contact angle measured at thermodynamic equilibrium is not equivalent to a dynamic contact angle. Since infiltration is a dynamic experiment, this technique is not valid and especially for polymers, because in equilibrium, most resins do wet fibres but after a long equilibrium time.

The second technique is based on the slug flow assumption where ΔP_γ is concentrated at the flow front. The pressure drop can therefore be deduced from infiltration experiments. Mortensen and Wong have applied this technique to measure ΔP_γ in Metal Matrix Composites [8]. In polymer composites, Ahn *et al.* [9] have tried to measure this capillary pressure drop. They used an Epon HPT 1071 resin from Shell but without any hardener. They have found various capillary pressures depending on the porosity for a woven fabric. Hammond and Loss [10] have used the same basis but their intentions were to measure the permeability and not the capillary pressure drop itself.

In this article, a technique has been developed in order to experimentally measure the capillary pressure drop. One type of Non-Crimp Fabric has been selected as the porous fibre bed and three different fluids were studied.

THEORY

The infiltration takes place either with constant flow rate or with constant pressure. In the two situations, the capillary forces can be determined. The main assumption is that the flow front is in accordance with the slug-flow assumption, where the fabric is either dry or fully impregnated [11].

Let us consider a volume defined by the cavity of the mould where a fibre bed of fibre volume fraction V_f is placed. Let us then imagine a liquid injected with an applied pressure, P_{app} . The pressure acting within the dry fibre bed is the atmospheric pressure, P_g . After a time t , the flow front has reached a position $L(t)$ as depicted in Figure 1. Darcy's law applied to one-directional flow, is:

$$v_o = -\frac{K}{\eta} \cdot \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \quad (2)$$

Where v_o is the superficial velocity, K is the permeability and η the viscosity.

Figure 1 – Description of the impregnation in a fibre preform.

If L is the position of the flow front, the continuity equation dictates that:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{dL}{dt} \right) = 0 \quad (3)$$

Here $\frac{dL}{dt}$ is the liquid velocity and is related with v_0 using equation (4), known as the Dupuit-Forchheimer approximation where Q is the flow rate and A the cross-section. This equation links the apparent velocity of the flow front and the true liquid velocity.

$$v_0 = \frac{Q}{A} = (1 - V_f) \cdot \frac{dL}{dt} \quad (4)$$

Finally the flow front moves as:

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = - \frac{K}{\eta(1 - V_f)} \cdot \frac{dP}{dx} \quad (5)$$

Constant pressure:

Under constant pressure, $\frac{dP}{dx}$ is equal to $\frac{\Delta P}{L(t)}$. Hence by integration of equation (5):

$$L^2 = \psi^2 \cdot t = - \frac{2K\Delta P}{\eta(1 - V_f)} \cdot t \quad (6)$$

In this equation, ψ^2 is a kinetics parameter, acting like a diffusion coefficient. By plotting the ψ^2 coefficient of several experiments lead at various applied pressures, as a function of the pressure difference ΔP , the capillary forces can be determined, when the ψ^2 coefficient equals 0. At this time the pressure drop exactly counteracts the capillary pressure ΔP_γ , and using equation(7), this pressure can be estimated.

$$\Delta P = P_g + \Delta P_\gamma - P_{app} \quad (7)$$

ΔP_γ is correctly named the capillary pressure drop and is by definition the difference between the pressure in the preform ahead of the infiltration front and the local pressure in the fluid just behind the infiltration front.

Constant flow rate:

Under constant flow rate, equation (5) remains valid. In this situation $\frac{dL}{dt}$ is constant and equal to $\frac{L}{t}$, where L is the total length of the fibre bed. Equation (8) can be obtained by substituting the total length by its expression using the flow rate and the time.

$$(P_g - P_{app}) = -\frac{Q^2 \eta}{A^2 K (1 - V_f)} \cdot t + \Delta P_\gamma \quad (8)$$

In this situation, the capillary pressure can be determined in a single experiment by plotting the pressure difference as a function of time. The value at time zero, that is when the flow front touches the fibre bed, is a direct measure of the capillary pressure, assuming that \dot{Q} remains constant.

EXPERIMENTAL

Three distinct experiments were conducted for this work. They all focussed on the infiltration of a specific liquid into a fibre preform. The different conditions for each series of experiments are as given in Table 1.

Table 1 – Experimental conditions.

Series of experiments	1	2	3
Type of liquid	Water + PEG	TS Epoxy	TP PA 12
Type of fabric	NCF (epoxy-sized)	NCF (epoxy-sized)	NCF (PA12-sized)
Type of infiltration	Constant pressure	Constant pressure	Constant flow rate
Temperature of infiltration	RT	100°C	190°C
Fibre volume fraction	55%	54%	53%

In the first series, a mixture of polyethylene glycol (PEG) and water was prepared in order to have a Newtonian fluid with known viscosity. The latter was measured with an ARES rheometer from Rheometrics using a Couette apparatus. Three different viscosities were tested in the 1st series. Values of 0.013Pas, 0.11Pas and 0.59Pas were hence selected.

The second liquid to be used in this study was an Epikote 828 LV epoxy from Shell, cured with Epikure DX 6514. The base is mixed with the hardener using a ratio of 100:17 in weight. When injected at a temperature of 80°C, the viscosity of the epoxy came down to a value of 0.08Pas and started to rise after 500s leaving enough time for injection.

The last liquid to be tested was a lauro lactam 12 from EMS-Chemie. This PA12 monomer was injected with its activator and catalyst. At a temperature of 190°C, the mixture of monomer and 2% of activator-catalyst had a viscosity in the range of 1mPas. Anionic polymerisation at this temperature started after 140s. This liquid system has been extensively studied by Luisier *et al.* [12-14] and Zingraff *et al.* [15].

The reinforcement bed was in the form of Non-Crimp Fabrics which are stacks of unidirectional carbon fibre plies stitched together with a PET thread. Biaxial fabrics with a

stacking sequence of $[\pm 45]$ were used in the present study. For PEG and epoxy liquids epoxy-sized fabrics were chosen. Since the use of lauro lactam 12 requires moisture and oxygen free environment, HTS 5N21 fibres from Tenax were used for manufacturing the NCFs suited for LC12 process.

Two moulds were manufactured for these tests. The former was used for room temperature conditions and was based on the design of Ken Han *et al.* [16]. Figure 2 shows a picture of this mould. The lower half mould is made out of steel whereas the upper half is made out of PMMA. Both halves are 2.5cm thick in order to prevent bending and therefore changes in the fibre volume fraction. The dimension of the fabric inside the mould was $77 \times 150 \text{mm}^2$.

The second mould was built to be used above 200°C . In the lower half, six heating cartridges are placed evenly. The upper mould is made out of glass reinforced with a steel frame in order to withstand the backpressure due to the fabric compaction. The dimension of the fabric used with this mould was $200 \times 120 \text{mm}^2$.

Figure 2 – Picture of the mould designed to be used at room temperature with PEG.

Figure 3 – Picture of the mould used with thermoset and thermoplastic resins.

Two different equipments were used in order to inject the liquids. For the PEG and for the epoxy an injection unit from Plastech (Cornwall, UK) was used. This unit is a single pot RTM machine where the liquid is first introduced in a pressure vessel and then injected into the mould at a given pressure to be chosen by the operator. For injecting LC12, a specific machine manufactured by Dosiplast (Balzers, FL) was selected. In this equipment the monomer and the solution containing both the activator and the catalyst are kept in two separate vessels. The monomer was held at temperature of 175°C under nitrogen in order to remain liquid. The two components were brought together with gear pumps into a mixing head kept at 190°C prior to injection.

A pressure transducer was placed just before the injection gate of the moulds in order to measure the applied pressure with a good accuracy even at high temperature. The sensor used at room temperature is up to 0.01bar accuracy. The sensor used with warm liquids is accurate up to 0.001bar.

The apparatus used during injection enabled the monitoring of the flow front using a TV-camera. Time, temperatures and pressures were hence recorded live.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In constant pressure experiment, from the image obtained via the camera the infiltration distance is related to time and pressure as shown in Figure 4. By plotting the square of distance as a function of time, a ψ^2 coefficient is determined as shown in Figure 5. One experiment leads to one value of this ψ^2 coefficient. The latter of course depends on the applied pressure and the viscosity as shown in equation (6).

Figure 4 – Picture obtained during the impregnation of PEG in NCF.

Figure 5 – Determination of the ψ^2 coefficient linking L^2 with the time t .

The ψ^2 coefficient is then reported to the pressure difference in a plot. Since the model liquid had 3 different viscosities, the ψ^2 coefficient is multiplied with the liquid viscosity. This product is hence plotted versus the pressure difference. This allows all experiments to be displayed in one single plot as depicted in Figure 6. According to what was demonstrated with equations (6) and (7), the capillary pressure ΔP_γ could be estimated. In the case of PEG, the value was as follows:

$$\Delta P_\gamma (PEG \& NCF) = -5.4kPa$$

Figure 6 – $\eta\psi^2$ coefficient of the PEG balanced with its viscosity, plotted versus the pressure difference.

Figure 7 – ψ^2 coefficient of the epoxy plotted versus the pressure difference.

From Figure 6, the ψ^2 coefficient found with the PEG at high viscosity is outside the range of values found. The linear regression is therefore calculated without this value. Had the value been accounted for, the resulting capillary pressure would have been -2.8kPa .

The determination of the capillary pressure with the epoxy system follows the same procedure. As all the experiments were conducted with the same viscosity, ψ^2 itself could be plotted versus the pressure difference as shown in Figure 7. The capillary pressure found with epoxy was:

$$\Delta P_{\gamma} (\text{Epoxy \& NCF}) = 13.9\text{kPa}$$

The injection pressure did not vary significantly when PEG was used. A relative difference of less than 1% was observed. The assumption of constant pressure withstands. When epoxy is concerned, the pressure did not reach a constant value at the start of the experiment. The pressure indeed required several seconds to reach the final pressure. Figure 8 shows that it took less than 5 seconds to reach the final applied pressure with PEG, whereas it took more than 30s to reach this final value in the case of epoxy. ψ^2 values should thus be taken after 30s within stationary regime in Figure 7.

Infiltration in the last series of experiments conducted with LC-12 was held with constant flow rate as the equipment injected the monomer and activator with gear pumps. With this condition, it was not necessary to record the location of the flow front during the entire procedure. Only the inlet pressure was vital as well as the precise time when the flow front touched the fabric.

Figure 9 shows the variation of the pressure difference acting at the injection gate for one experiment. At point 1, at the very beginning of the injection, the first infiltration required almost no pressure. It means the capillary forces were acting as a help for the infiltration. As the flow proceeds, the fibre bed resistance to flow increases and so does the pressure. At point 2, the flow front reached the end of the fabric, and even though the liquid was still being injected, no pressure increase was observed any more. Point 3 on the curve indicates the closing of the injection gate prior to the stopping of the injection machine.

Figure 8 – Difference of time for reaching steady state conditions for PEG and for epoxy.

Figure 9 – Determination of the capillary pressure from plots giving pressure difference vs. time.

As observed on Figure 9, at the first stage of the injection the pressure increase was not linear. After a certain period of time, the pressure became linear. From equation (8), it appears that the increase of pressure is supposed to be linear. Due to the time necessary to reach the steady-state conditions, it was relevant to apply a linear regression on the second half of the curve, as shown with the line on Figure 9. The intersection of the latter with the Y-axis gives the value of the capillary pressure. By averaging the different values, the capillary pressure of LC12 was found to be:

$$\Delta P_{\gamma} (LC12 \& NCF) = -13.8\text{kPa}$$

The “constant flow rate” series of experiments is less reliable than the “constant pressure” series. An error of $\pm 6.4\text{kPa}$ was observed. Constant flow rate experiments also require a large number of experiments to obtain reliable values. In order to determine whether the two methods for determining the capillary pressure are comparable, additional experiments with the same epoxy will be performed later in a gear pump injection unit.

The series of experiments held under constant pressure was also subjected to errors which were estimated to a value of $\pm 1\text{kPa}$. It is important to note that the value of capillary pressure determined through out this work is defined from a dynamic response. As mentioned in the introduction, many authors use the determination of the contact angle and the surface tension in order to determine the capillary pressure.

In the case of epoxy on fibres, contact angles on the order of 20-30° are commonly reported, hence the value of capillary pressure calculated using equation (1) should be negative. The opposite is found in the dynamic case, where velocity is driven by an applied pressure. This is most probably due to the resin viscosity which increases the value of the “apparent” wetting angle θ . The dependence of θ on the infiltration velocity will be checked later with the constant flow rate experiments with epoxy.

On the other hand PEG and LC12 are found to enhance the flow for infiltration. Since PEG is a surfactant dissolved in water with a surface tension of 46mN/m, this behaviour was expected. For LC12 the value of contact angle is not known on the fibres because the polymer crystallises, rendering its measurement difficult. From our experience, it can be inferred that wetting is favourable for LC12 on carbon fibres, and that the low viscosity of the monomer allows the phenomenon to take place close to the thermodynamic equilibrium. The value found is significant compared to the applied pressure in the LC12 injection of 100kPa. It also indicates that for short distances, one could infiltrate the fabric with capillary effects only.

The results found herein are in agreement with values found in the literature. Using the data obtained by Ahn *et al.* [9], and fitting the parameters according to the present work, a capillary pressure of 15000Pa is found. This value corresponds well to what is found in the present work for epoxy. The paper however does not specify whether the capillary pressure act to help or to prevent the flow advancement. Amico and Lekakou found in their paper [17] a value, for the capillary pressure, of 9216Pa, using silicon oil for the experimentation. This value of capillary pressure is also within the range of values found in the present work.

CONCLUSIONS

Two methods were developed in the present work to measure the capillary pressure drop acting when a fibre bed is being infiltrated by a liquid matrix. Under constant injection pressure, the capillary pressure could be determined from the ψ^2 versus pressure values. Values of -5.5kPa and 13.9kPa were found with PEG and Epoxy respectively. Infiltration is thus spontaneous in the case of PEG. For epoxy, the value shows that a certain threshold pressure has to be overcome and that the system is out of the thermodynamic equilibrium during injection. The second method was used with LC12 and consisted in using constant flow rate conditions for injection. The accurate measurement of pressure as a function of time enabled the calculation of the capillary pressure for LC12. A value of -13.8kPa indicated that capillary effects had a positive effect on impregnation. In the case of epoxy, the capillary pressure drop is somehow low compared to typical injection pressures of 5 to 10bar. Whereas in the LC12 system, where injection is performed at 1bar, the capillary pressure drop cannot be neglected (~15% of applied pressure), and has a positive effect on impregnation.

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